

GEOLOGICAL AND GEOTECHNICAL APPRAISAL DURING CONSTRUCTION OF UPSTREAM SURGE CHAMBERS AND SHAFTS - A CASE STUDY OF TEHRI PUMPED STORAGE PLANT (1000MW)

Sanjay Dave* & Rajeev Prasad**

* Sr. Vice President, Hydroelectric Projects, Hindustan Construction Co. Ltd., Mumbai, India

** Chief Geologist, Hindustan Construction Co. Ltd., Mumbai, India

Cite This Article: Sanjay Dave & Rajeev Prasad, "Geological and Geotechnical Appraisal During Construction of Upstream Surge Chambers and Shafts - A Case Study of Tehri Pumped Storage Plant (1000MW)", International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research, Volume 9, Issue 2, July - December, Page Number 119-129, 2024.

Copy Right: © DV Publication, 2024 (All Rights Reserved). This is an Open Access Article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium provided the original work is properly cited.

Abstract:

Inadequate geological and geotechnical investigation may lead to over-budgeting, schedule overrun, and serious loss of safety. Geological surveys which include proper assessment and investigation of geological strata are essential for any kind of projects especially for large and most expensive structures like dams and hydropower plants. In the case of Tehri Pumped Storage Plant which is in EPC mode possess lot of challenges during construction stage. As an integral part of Tehri Hydropower Complex (THPC) located in the Uttarakhand State of Northern India; an underground 4x250 MW Tehri Pumped Storage Plant (TPSP) parallel and close to the existing 1000 MW Tehri Hydro Power (HPP). Tehri PSP is located on the left bank of Bhagirathi River in the district of Tehri about 1.5 km downstream on its confluence with river Bhilangana. The major project components are Machine Hall, Upstream Chambers and Shafts, Butterfly Valve Chamber (BVC), Penstock Assembly Chamber (PAC), Down Stream Surge Shafts, a pair of TRT's and outlet structures are in construction stage. The arrangement consists of surge shafts with Surge Chambers at the top of each shaft and is in poor geology with rock cover of 175.00m to 230.00m. The chambers were relocated and resized from the originally planned span due to poor geological conditions which called for a transition in an excavation with milk cane shape varies from 15.60m chamber invert to 25.50m diameter circular surge shaft.

This paper represents the geological and geotechnical appraisal encountered during excavation of both the upstream surge chambers (37.50m long X 15.00m wide X 15.00m high) and shafts with remedial measures using NATM construction methodology as well as proper excavation sequence. Strengthening of rock mass by adopting proper design measures from day-to-day monitoring instrument data of deformation as well as suitable construction methodology with highlighting the importance of orientation of structure with respect to prominent joint sets. Reinforced self-compact concrete lining using jump form shutter and grouting plays a very important role to complete the tasks in a specified time period, which is also briefly discussed in this article,

Key Words: Poor Geology, Deformation Analysis, Construction Methodology, Reinforced Self-Compact Concrete Lining, Grouting

Introduction:

Construction of any Hydro Power project in Himalayas are dominated by high hills and steep slopes. Underground excavations are very challenging due to fragile geology, tectonic activities and complex geological structure. In tectonically active young mountains like the Himalayas, the rocks found during tunnelling are relatively incompetent and affected by a number of folds, faults and thrusts of various scales and at many places are heavily charged with underground water (Goel, 2014; Siddique et al., 2017). There was lot of constraints initially to finalise the layout of Approach Adit of Upstream Surge Chambers/ Shaft termed as AA-1 and later on Up Stream Surge Chambers and Shafts due to poor geological conditions. The major geological problems experienced, and their possible remedial measures are briefly discussed in following sections. Weak rocks often form up a big part of the shallow stratum all over the world (Sharma and Tiwari, 2012). Therefore, they build up the foundation ground of many construction projects as e.g. deep construction pits, tunnel excavations and open cast mines. However, the extent for investigating the behaviour of these rock types in building projects rarely corresponds to their frequency and to the engineering geological problems they cause. The construction, in recent years, of tunnels through low strength anisotropic rocks such as phyllites, shales and schists in the Himalayan regions has generated new thoughts in anticipating and assessing the problems posed by such rocks. The problems faced in tunnelling through these rocks include squeezing ground if the rock contains a considerable amount of clay minerals and loosening of the rock mass in the case of layered and jointed rock masses. Loosening results in the separation of the rock mass from the main body and produces a dead load (Bhasin et al., 1995). In this paper Geological and Geotechnical appraisal during construction of Upstream Surge Chambers and Shafts are discussed with a reference to layout fixation of relevant structures, methodology of excavation and encountered problems as well as their remedial measures are discussed. Further use of Geotechnical monitoring instruments during construction stage and Reinforced Self Concrete lining, which is first time applied in deep underground Hydropower Structures are also discussed.

Figure 1-TEHRI PSP- 3D LAYOUT

Figure 2- Upstream Surge Chamber and Shaft

Background:

Tehri PSP has been envisaged to generate 1000 MW of peaking power for enhancing system reliability and provide balancing load to the thermal and renewable generation during off peak hours. The reservoir created by the Tehri Dam and Koteshwar Dam would function as upstream and downstream reservoir for Tehri Pumped Storage Plant. This Plant will contribute to stabilization a big way by meet the peak load and balance requirement. Tehri PSP comprising of four reversible pump turbine units of 250 mw each, involve construction of an underground machine hall on the left bank of river Bhagirathi. The main feature of the project is the large variation of 90m between maximum and minimum head under which the reversible units shall operate. The operation of Tehri PSP is based on concept of recycling of water discharged between upper reservoir to lower reservoir, on completion additional generating capacity of 1000 MW, peaking power will be added to northern region (annual generation of 2475 million units). For pumping operation of reversible units, the off-peak energy requirement will be the order of 3104 MU. With the construction of Tehri PSP Tehri hydro complex shall function as a major peaking station having an installed capacity of 2400 MW.

Study Area:

Regional Geology:

Tehri Project area lies within the Main Himalayan Block (MHB), in the midlands of Lesser Himalayas, bounded to the north and south by regional tectonic lineaments - the Main Central Thrust (MCT) and Main Boundary Fault (MBF) respectively. The former, to the north separates the meta-sedimentary sequence of Lesser Himalaya from the crystalline rocks of Higher Himalaya and the latter marks boundary between lesser Himalaya and tertiary sequence of Frontal Foothill Belt (FFB), in the south. The rock stratigraphy of lesser Himalaya exposed around the Tehri Project area are broadly classified into Garhwal, Simla, Jaunsar, Bailana, Krol and Tal groups. The folded metasedimentary rocks exposed around the project site form an uninterrupted sequence of Chandpur Phyllites having a variable proportion of argillaceous and arenaceous constituents. Considering the rhythmicity of intercalated bands and varied the degree of tectonic effects in them, the Phyllites at project side has been classified into mainly four lithological variants. Rock mass in this area are mainly variants of Phyllites and are classified as below: -

- Phyllitic Quartzite Massive (PQM)*
- Phyllitic Quartzite Thinly Bedded (PQT)*
- Sheared/Schistose Phyllite (SP)*

PQM and PQT are more quartzite (arenaceous) and rarely micaceous in composition and are coarser in grain size. These rocks are grey, dark grey, brownish grey, greenish grey, greyish grey and green in colour. It is mainly comprised of quartz, feldspar and oriented leths of micaceous minerals. QP is more areno-argillaceous in composition, fine-grained and dark colored. SP comprises of argillaceous and deformed variants of PQM and PQT rock, formed in sheared zone area which has weak rock mass characteristics.

Site Specific Geology:

Upstream Surge Chamber 3:

Crown portion of Upstream Surge Chamber-3 has been excavated throughout its length PQM, PQT with SP belonging to Chandpur Phyllites of Jaunsar group. The rock mass is foliated, jointed, slightly weathered and sheared at places. The Chamber encountered the following:

- PQM with PQT and SP in its initial length of 0.00 to 14.00m
- PQT with SP in a stretch of 15.00m i.e. 14.00 to 29.00m
- PQT with PQM from 29.00 to 37.50m

Generally, these rocks exhibit a dip ranging between 45°-50°/N180°-210° intersected by foliation planes dipping at 35°-45°/N140°-170°. Notably, there is significant silicification along both bedding and foliation joints, easily observable. Total no. of 24 shear zones have been encountered aligned along the bedding joints plane. These Shear Zones are classified based on thickness of infilling clay gauge.

- Minor Shears less than 5cm thick
- Thin Shears 5 to 10cm thick
- Major Shears more than 10 cm thick

The rock mass encountered ranging from El: -875.00 to 860.00 falls under the RMR class III and IV. Specifically, out of 37.50m length of the chamber, 14.00m is categorised as class III, while 23.50m falls under the class IV.

Upstream Surge Chamber 4:

The rock formation predominantly comprises Phyllitic quartzite in massive form, along with thinly bedded Phyllitic quartzite (PQM+PQT) and thinly bedded Phyllitic quartzite intermixed with sheared phyllite (PQT+SP). These rocks exhibit a general dip of 45°-55°/N180°-210°, intersected by foliation plane dipping at 35°-45°/N140°-170°.

13 shears of varying thickness have been encountered and categorized as minor, thin and major shears primarily following bedding traces. Additionally, Sheared Phyllite are observed in the crown portion towards the chamber's end and side walls from El: -861.00 to 859.00m. Based on encountered RMR values Chamber 4 rock class IV and III.

Design Approach for the Finalisation of Layout of Upstream Surge Chambers and Shafts:

During initial stage of project topography and surface geological mapping was carried out to finalised the layout of various components. Considering the case of approach adit of upstream surge chamber and shaft faces lot of geological constraints. Ultimately after discussion with design consultants' location was finalised and accordingly excavation was started. Around 90% length of Adit was supported by structural steel support and rest 10% with rock bolt shotcrete and wire mesh. After visualizing the encountered rock in Approach Adit again a question raise about the location and layout of Surge Chambers and Shafts, because the initial layout of both the upstream Surge Shafts were aligned with a common chamber as shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: Proposed common chamber for both upstream surge shaft

However, due to poor geological condition during construction this idea was dropped and decided to change the alignment with separate chambers of each shaft.

To finalise the location of chamber and shafts Geotechnical investigation was proposed for both Upstream surge Chamber/Shaft-3 and 4.

Geotechnical Investigation:

Drilling of Core Hole:

Sub - surface exploration for any underground structure is done by drilling of core holes at different location along the proposed alignment of the structure. Total 06 nos. of drill holes have been done to investigate the to investigate the subsurface condition and behaviour of rock mass. The details of core holes are given in table 1.

S.No	Hole No.	RD/Location	Size of hole	Length of hole	Angle with horizontal	Start date	Finish date	Remark
1.	CH - 3	US SS chamber above HRT-3	NX	100 m	90* downward	31/09/2013	07/11/2013	For PJT / dilatometer test& lab test at various depth
2.	CH - D	48	NX	6 m	90* upward	11/05/2015	12/03/2015	
3.	CH - F	48	NX	5 m	90* downward	10/03/2015	17/03/2015	
4.	CH - E	46	NX	5 m	0* right side	13/03/2015	16/03/2015	
5.	CH - G	48	NX	5 m	0* left side	12/03/2015	13/03/2015	
6.	BH-1	HRT-4 chainage 1069.0 m upward direction	NX	100.10 m	90* downward	23/07/2007	18/08/2007	By GSI to visualize the rock strata during DPR stage.

Table 1:- Details of core hole drilled in the adit of Upstream chamber - 3&4

Figure 3: Location of insitu test conducted in core hole.

Laboratory and Insitu Testing of Rock Mass Deformability:

Uniaxial compressive strength test has been Plate Jack test and Flexible Dilatometer has been conducted at Chamber-3 Upstream Surge Shaft location, Rd:-46.0m inside adit AA-1. The test depth for flexible dilatometer were spaced at 1.50 to 2.00m , starting from a depth of 1.40 to 4.38m including all core holes to avoid and disturbed zone. However, the total deformation moduli representing the rock mass under influence of the total applied pressure based on three loading and unloading cycle is presented in table 2.

Ch.no.	Depth (m)	Dilatometer Modulus(GPa)										
		CycleI(8GPa)			CycleII(12GPa)			CycleIII(20GPa)			Geology	
		Ed	Ee	Ee/Ed	Ed	Ee	Ee/Ed	Ed	Ee	Ee/Ed	RQD (%)	Rock Type
CH-G	4.30m	0.47	1.04	2.21	1.21	1.44	1.19	1.87	2.18	1.16	94	PQM
	2.20m	0.97	1.89	1.94	2.37	2.73	1.15	3.35	3.47	1.04	37	PQM with PQT
CH-E	1.40m	0.67	1.56	2.32	2.14	2.40	1.12	3.41	3.74	1.10	38	PQT
	4.38m	1.38	2.31	1.67	3.04	3.14	1.03	4.24	6.77	1.60	HIGH	PQT with PQM
CH-D	4.10m	1.22	2.49	2.04	3.42	3.63	1.06	5.35	5.93	1.11	45	PQM and PQT
	2.10m	0.85	1.42	1.67	1.37	1.81	1.32	1.89	2.50	1.32	48	PQM
CH-F	2.70m	1.53	2.68	1.76	3.35	3.74	1.12	5.03	5.56	1.11	30	PQT with PQM
	4.10m	1.52	2.33	1.53	2.43	2.89	1.19	2.69	4.41	1.64	43	PQT with PQM

Ed= Deformation Modulus, Ee= Elastic Modulus

Table 2: Deformation and Elastic Moduli obtained from Flexible Dilatometer Test at PJT location

The Flexible Dilatometer test moduli results for rock mass at various depths for core holes CH-D, CH-E, CH-F and CH-G was obtained and it has been concluded that the rock mass at the bottom and left side of niche is apparently weaker than that the top and right side of it. The objective was to define the deformation characteristics of the rock mass broadly classified in to two categories viz PQT+PQM and PQT+SP. However the appropriate moduli for any engineering design application shall be selected by the designers as per the anticipated structural behaviour of the rock mass.

Engineering Geological Mapping of Central Gullet of Upstream Surge Chamber 3 and 4:

Three-dimensional geological mapping was carried out in central gullet of upstream surge chamber-3 and 4 for a cumulative length of 37.50m to suggest measures for rock support and to evaluate the chambers stability as well as planning for further excavation. Wet to damp conditions were observed and Poor to Fair rock mass was observed throughout. Joint planes are rough to slightly rough in nature. RQD ranges from <25% to 50% as mentioned in table 3.

RD (M)		RMR	Rock Class	Remarks
From	To			
0	11	49	III	Heading and Benching from EL 875 to 860 M
11	14	46	III	
17	23	35	IV	
23	37.5	38	IV	

Table 3: Rock Class encountered in Upstream chamber 3

RD (M)		RMR	Rock Class	Remarks
From	To			
0	10	41	III	Heading and benching from EL 875 to 860 M
10	17	40	IV	
17	21	44	III	
21	25	41	III	
25	32	49	III	
32	37.5	30	IV	

Table 4: Rock Class encountered in Upstream chamber 4

Methodology Adopted for Construction:

As stated above central gulleets for both the chambers were already excavated. The invert slope of upper chamber-3 is horizontal while upper chamber- 4 is in 1:7 gradient. Grouting galleries were proposed for both the chambers as shown in figure 4.

Figure 4: General Arrangement plan and section of Upstream Surge Shaft Chamber

These galleries were used for construction and in operation period for identifying the saturation conditions and its remedial measurements. Grouting Gallery-3 (R/S) started from EL:-860.00m with a length of 88.00m touch the chambers crown at EL:-875.00m and L/S grouting gallery-3 with a length of 85.00m opened at EL:-860.00m. R/S gallery used for Heading ,side slashing and benching. Some part of benching was carried out through grouting gallery left side. Heading and Systematic benching was carried out with proper drill and blast pattern. Blast monitoring was observed for each blast to know the Peak Particle velocity. Observed PPV is .60 to 1.25mm/sec, which was n permissible limit.

Grouting Gallery 4 is existing around the Upstream chamber-4 with a length of 155. 00m. Central gullet, side slashing was carried out properly with proper benching as per blasting norms relevant to encountered rock class.

Rock class-III and IV encountered in both the chambers and rock support system was provided as per approved GFC drawing. Details are given in figure 5 and 6.

Figure 5: Rock support system in Upper chamber 3

Figure 7:-Rock Support System in Upper chamber 4

After completion of both the surge chambers discussion was held with designers regarding the shape and size two dimensional model studies was proposed.

Model Studies of Upstream Surge Chamber and Shafts:

Based on 3D geological mapping of chambers and core hole data of CH-3 and BH-1 geological model was prepared. The discontinuity data is summarized in table 5

Joint Set	Avg. Dip Amount	Avg. Dip Direction	Persistence
J1	50°	195°	3-10m
J2	40°	197°	
J3	60°	20°	
J4	67°	290°	

Table 5: Discontinuity data based on geological mapping

Geological, Geotechnical and Hydrological input data for the conduct of stability analysis of such type of large underground component has been considered in the analysis as per rock cover at upstream surge shaft location. Two stress levels are considered due to considerable height of shafts Summary of insitu stress is shown in Table: -6

Particulars	Rock cover 270m (El. 780 - 860)	Rock cover 350m (El. 730 - 780)
Vertical stress in Mpa	7.29	9.45
Maximum horizontal stress ratio		1.2
Minimum horizontal stress ratio		0.9

Maximum horizontal stress in MPa	8.75	11.34
Minimum horizontal stress in MPa	6.56	8.51

Table 6: Summary of In-situ test

Note

1. Geological section upto EL 830m, prepared based on the geology encountered in chamber-3.
2. From EL 830m to 750m section prepared based on the geology projected from drill hole CH-03.
3. Below EL 750m section prepared based on the geology projected from Lower Horizontal Penstocks and Power House.
4. All the shears (Major & Minor) projected from drill hole CH-01 and encountered in chamber -03, and shears are trending towards joint set J1 except shear zone encountered at RD25 (m) of chamber traversing along the joint set J2.
5. All the shears (Major & Minor) contained clay filled gaugy material.

References:

1. EDF Report no. D309514008817
2. Drill hole log CH-01 and CH-03
3. 3D Geological log of US Surge shaft chamber-3 and Chamber-4
4. 3D Geological log of Lower Horizontal Penstocks, Power House, BVC and PAC
5. Water level 860.187m observed from drill hole CH-03 on dated 7th Nov.2013

Figure 8: Geological section of Upstream Surge shafts

The geotechnical parameters of various rock units were adopted based on investigations results and empirical correlation.

Rock Category	Parameters		Rock class			
			Class - II	Class - III	Class - IV	Class - V
Intact Rock	GSI _{mean}	[--]	50	42	30	25
	m _i	[--]	10	10	10	10
	UCS	[MPa]	96	72	50	48
	Poission's Ratio, ν	[--]	0.22	0.23	0.25	0.25
	Bulk Density, γ	[kN/m ³]	27	27	27	27
Peak	Elastic Modulus, E _m	[GPa]	16.0	11.0	5.0	3.5
	Cohesion, c ^{peak}	[MPa]	2.53	1.93	1.35	1.29
Residual	Friction Angle, φ ^{peak}	[°]	40.9	36.3	29	27.3
	Cohesion, c ^{res}	[MPa]	0.99	0.85	0.7	0.52
	Friction Angle, φ ^{res}	[°]	36.1	33.3	28.5	27.7

Table 7: Geotechnical parameters consider for analysis

The rock mass surrounding the excavation has been assumed to be homogeneous and isotropic in all directions and modified based on Mohr- Coulomb failure criterion. Support system is assumed to be after excavation of one round which results

in relaxation of stresses up to 70%. Four sets of joints are considered for wedge formation. The analysis of geometry and stability of the underground wedges is defined by intersection of joints of the rock mass surrounding the shaft performed on the scale of UNWEDGE software. Different combination of all joints were analysed. Support System of 35 KN with fully grouted rock bolts, 10.0m long and 1.50m C/C was adopted for the stability of wedges after installation of rock support. All wedges were found stable with more than 1.50 Factor of safety.

Excavation Sequence for the execution of Shaft:

Excavation of twin shafts was the big challenges due to its complex geological conditions and its large diameter. Raise climber was used for the opening of 3.0m diameter in upward direction of Pilot Shaft from HRT-3 and 4 with the help of Alamac Raise Climber. The widening of pilot shaft has been taken into consideration for sequential excavation and approved support system from top to bottom for both the shafts.

Figure 9: Pilot Shaft by Raise Climber

To control shaft deformation and to restrict of explosive consumption, taking in view the vicinity of shafts close to already operating HPP, the widening of shaft has been modelled as the half face excavation. The control blast design adopted to restrict Peak Particle Velocity and to delimit over excavation of both the shafts in the poor rock conditions.

To determine the structural behaviour of rock mass Multipoint bore hole extensometer (MPBX) and load cells were installed during excavation. Readings of these geotechnical instruments were carried out based on frequency specified by designers. Yet another is the BI-Reflector target used to know the 3D movement of excavated face of the shafts.

PQT+PQM and PQT+SP rock encountered throughout in both the shafts during excavation. Proper drill and blast pattern was used during excavation. For the collar beam and slant portion, excavation was carried out safely with approved rock in each round and further excavation of circular shaft was carried out in six stages with approved drill blast pattern.

The rock mass traversed by four sets of joint sets through out the shafts including bedding and foliation joint (Set No.-1 and 2) with a persistence of about 15-20m, but generally ranges from 3- 10m)..Set No. 3 and 4 exhibit shorter persistence 5-7m. These joints have separation of about .1 to 1.0mm and are spaced at 6-90cm, with slightly rough surface. The observed infilling material is soft with a thickness of about 5mm.

Based on encountered RMR value Class-III and IV rock encountered during excavation of Surge Shaft-3 and 4. Details are mention in table 8 and 9

Elevation(m)	RMR value	Rock Class	category	%age
860.00 - 792.00	28-40	IV	Poor	32.5
792.00 - 716.00	42-49	III	Fair	67.5

Table 8: RMR value and percentage of rock class encountered in Upstream Surge Shaft-3

Elevation(m)	RMR Value	Rock Class	Category	% age
860.00 - 830.00	38- 40	IV	Poor	15.0
830.00 - 795.00	42 -45	III	Fair	26.2
795.00-778.00	31 -36	IV	Poor	12.7
778.00 - 772.00	42	III	Fair	4.5
772.00- 752.00	36	IV	Poor	15.0
752.00 - 716.00	42- 43	III	Fair	26.6

Table 9: RMR value and percentage of rock class encountered in Upstream Surge Shaft-4

Rock Support system in both the Shafts were provided based on rock class and at some locations where adverse geology encountered additional support was provided Length of drainage holes were increased at various locations where seepage/dripping observed. Treatment of major cavity encountered in upstream Surge shat-4i between El:-752.00 to 782.00m was tackled properly with the help of backfill concrete of M15 grade and consolidation grouting stage wise. Rock class -IV was provided in this area with an additional length of rock bolts to stitch the back fill concrete and rock. Drainage holes were also provided to release the water seepage at various location of cavity. Section and Photograph shown in figure 10 and 11 respectively indicates real picture of cause behind the occurrence of cavity.

Figure 10: Section and Pictorial view of Upstream Surge Shft-4

Figure 11: Cavity at Upstream Surge Shaft-4 between El:-752.00 to 782.00m

Component	Rock Class	Elevation(m)		Rock Support Provided	Shotcrete	Reinforced Girder
Up Stream Surge Shaft-3	IV	860.00	792.00	32Ø, 10.00 m long rock bolt@1.00m C/C	300mm thick shotcrete with two layers of wire mesh	Reinforced girder @ 1.00m C/C
	III	792.00	716.00	32Ø , 8.00m long rock bolt @ 1.50m C/C	200 mm thick shotcrete with two layers of wire mesh	
Up Stream Surge Shaft-4	IV	860.00	830.00	32Ø, 10.00 m long rock bolt@1.00m C/C	300mm thick shotcrete with two layers of wiremesh	Reinforced girder @ 1.00m C/C
	III	830.00	795.00	32Ø , 8.00m long rock bolt @ 1.50m C/C	200 mm thick shotcrete with two layers of wire mesh	
	IV	795.00	778.00	32Ø, 10.00 m long rock bolt@1.00m C/C	300mm thick shotcrete with two layers of wiremesh	Reinforced girder @ 1.00m C/C
	III	778.00	772.00	32Ø , 8.00m long rock bolt @ 1.50m C/C	200 mm thick shotcrete with two layers of wire mesh	
	IV	772.00	752.00	32Ø, 10.00 m long rock bolt@1.00m C/C	300mm thick shotcrete with two layers of wiremesh	Reinforced girder @ 1.00m C/C
	III	752.00	716.00	32Ø , 8.00m long rock bolt @ 1.50m C/C	200 mm thick shotcrete with two layers of wire mesh	

Table 10: Details of Rock Support System installed in both the Shafts during excavation

After completion of both the chambers and shafts seepage/dripping /dampness was observed from crown portion even though drainage holes were provided during excavation. Further it has been decided to provide 76Ø deep drainage holes from both the grouting galleries in the form umbrellato release the water seepage above the crown portion for stability

Reinforced Concrete Lining and Grouting:

Reinforced concrete lining in 145.00m deep shaft is a big task to complete within a specified time and limit. Jump form shutter is used for lining and keeping view of quality control and saving of time M25A10.Self Compact Concrete used .in both the shafts with reinforcement as per approved drawing. Average 3-4 lift (i.e.12.00 to 16.00m) concrete lining was completed in a month. At present concrete lining of both the shafts has been completed as shown in figure:-12 &13.

Figure 12 & 13: Shows present status of Upstream Surge Shaft-3 and 4

Contact grouting is not required in Self compact concrete lining only consolidation grouting has been carried out in Class-IV rock. In Upstream Surge Shaft-3 grouting was completed up to EL:-837.50m and balance 22.50m to be carried out from top of shaft and through grouting gallery. Same methodology will be adopted for Upstream Surge shaft-4 as mentioned in Figure:-14 and 15. Overall, it can be prescribed that for the speediness and time saving Self Concrete lining is the best solution to achieve the targets in a given milestones.

Fig 14 : Arrangement of consolidation grouting pattern in Slant portion of Upstream surge shaft - 3

Conclusion:

The construction of both the Upstream Surge Chambers and Shafts faces geological conditions represent a critical phase and it involves multiple stages for its completion. It becomes more critical when adverse geology was encountered. Achieving the excavation of chambers and shafts with a reducing dimension of chambers based on innovative design and geotechnical parameters with a transition between shaft and chambers. Successful completion of excavation based on geotechnical monitoring is an achievable task. Tackling of cavity in upstream surge shaft-4 with suitable methodology. Reinforcement Concrete lining by Self Compact Concrete is a remarkable achievement with a stipulated time frame with a jump form shutter in such a big shaft is appreciable. The achievement demonstrates the effectiveness of proper planning and adaptability in ensuring design and success of construction with challenges.

Acknowledgements:

Authors are very much thankful to the management of THDC India Ltd. and M/S Hindustan Construction Company Ltd. for providing the necessary support to carry out the work.

References:

1. Bhasin, R., Barton, N., Grimstad, E., Chryssanthakis, P., 1995. Engineering geological characterization of low strength anisotropic rocks in the Himalayan region for assessment of tunnel support. *Eng. Geol.* 40, 169-193. doi:10.1016/0013-7952(95)00055-0
2. Carter, T.G., 2011. Himalayan Ground Conditions challenge innovation for successful TBM Tunnelling.
3. Goel, R.K., 2014. Tunnelling through weak and fragile rocks of Himalayas. *Int. J. Min. Sci. Technol.* 24, 783-790. doi:10.1016/j.ijmst.2014.10.008
4. Hoek, E., Guevara, R., 2009. Overcoming Squeezing in the Yacambu 42, 389-418. doi:10.1007/s00603-009-0175-5
5. Khali, Rakesh, Bahuguna, Naveen, 2020, Managing Geological complexity in Engineering and construction of Tunnels, *Journal of CE & CR* ,PP.28-32
6. Sharma, H.R., Tiwari, A.N., 2012. Tunneling in Himalayan Region :Geological Problems and Solutions. *Int. Water Power Dam Construction.*,64 , PP.14-19
7. Siddique, T., Pradhan, S.P., Vishal, V., Mondal, M.E.A., Singh, T.N., 2017. Stability assessment of road cut slopes along National Highway -58. *India Environ. Earth Science* .76, PP.1-18. doi:10.1007/s12665-017-7091-x
8. Detailed Project Report of Tehri Pumped Storage Plant(1000 MW), Unpublished report
9. Excavation sequences for slashing of Upstream Surge Shaft No. 3 & 4. May 2017. Tehri Pumped Storage Plant.
10. Final report on Plate Jack Test and Flexible Dilatometer Test at Upstream Shaft locations in 2015
11. Tehri PSP- Geological & Geotechnical input data for conduct calculations on the stability of upstream surge shaft. Document no.: 309514008817 Date: 25-07-2014.